

TONGUE DIAGNOSTICS: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF ITS APPLICATIONS IN CLINICAL AND TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

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Introduction. The tongue is a multifunctional organ that acts as an essential pathophysiological diagnostic tool across ancient and modern medicine. The surface of the tongue, characterized by papillae and taste buds, exhibits visibly changing patterns in the face of certain systemic health conditions. Traditionally, ancient forms of medicine, such as TCM, have mapped special parts of the tongue to internal organs and have clinically evaluated changes in color, texture, or coating for the diagnosis of diseases. In modern clinical medicine, examination of the tongue provides noninvasive insights into conditions such as diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, deficiencies of nutrients, rheumatic diseases, and chronic kidney disease.

The purpose of this study. This study aims at the analysis of the tongue color, coating, and morphology with regard to their accordance with modern diagnostics and their ability in early disease detection. Bridging the gap between the two paradigms, the aim is to integrate tongue diagnostics into clinical care for better patient outcomes.

Materials and methods. A total of 50 patients (24 male and 26 female), aged 18 to 77 years, were randomly selected from the Rheumatology (21), Cardiology (9), Vascular Surgery (10), and Nephrology (10) departments. Two female patients opted out, which left 48 patients for analysis. Tongue images were photographed via devices during clinical examination and interview. Observed changes in tongue color, coating, and morphology were analyzed alongside reported symptoms and preliminary diagnoses. These findings were compared with definitive diagnoses obtained through modern laboratory and instrumental tests documented in medical records. The data were further pooled and subjected to statistical analysis to allow meaning to be drawn.

The results of the study. Within the study, results were divided into three categories: matched, partially matched, and no match. 14 patients in Rheumatology out of 19 showed consistent tongue manifestations while 5 did

not. In Cardiology, only 8 patients were able to match, whereas 1 failed. From Vascular Surgery, 6 were fully matched, 2 matched partially, and 2 showed no connection. In Nephrology, 9 patients matched, and 1 did not. 36 patients out of the larger cohort (75%) exhibited precise matching between tongue changes and organ involvement; of these, 2 (4%) had, at best, partial match, while 10 (21%) showed no match at all. The results referenced set the verification for tongue examination for organ pathology diagnosis potential.

Conclusion. Tongue diagnosis has, for centuries, mirrored the general health of the individual on such parameters as inflammation, metabolic processes, and pathological alterations. While there have been advances in modern diagnostic procedures, tongue examination has its worth, particularly in an emergency setting, whereby the necessary tests could be identified and unwanted examinations avoided. This study supports that tongue diagnostics provide a preliminary insight into the condition of the patient and can be a good adjunct in clinical practice.

